

The Covid Vaccine Lie

Introduction

According to Prescott Harley Klein, vaccination is defined as follows (2007):

A vaccine [lat. vacca, cow] is a preparation of one or more microbes Antigens used to induce protective immunity. It can exist of killed microorganisms, living, weakened microorganisms (attenuated Vaccination); inactivated bacterial toxins (toxoids); cleaned cellular subunits; recombinant vectors (e.g. modified polio vaccine); or DNA(1).

The Covid “vaccines” are engineered mRNA products that don't fall under the definition of vaccines. The mRNA codes were created by computer simulations using bioinformatics analysis. A computer selects base sequences from an existing gene bank based on two requirements, sequences that can most effectively be implemented in the human body and genes that are most stable to be transported in a nanocarrier.

The gene sequences were not previously tested for safety or efficacy as is usual in clinical trials. And even if so, clinical trials on animals cannot determine safe implementation in the human body. The process of computer-assisted selection of suitable genes for carrier delivery in 'vaccine' is known as Reverse Vaccinology(2).

Studies suggest that mRNA antigens have certain advantages over DNA antigens. The antigen of a pathogen can be produced in the protein synthesis from an injected mRNA. The mRNA can be translated directly in the cytoplasm since the genetic code no longer requires translation in human nuclei (3).

The first mRNA therapies were only tested 2010 on mice in influenza “vaccines” (4). Because of known instability and toxic immunogenicity, mRNA therapies were not further used in humans.

Unfortunately, this has changed with the Covid "vaccines". According to studies, since then the mRNA has been modified to reduce the immunogenicity and to increase the stability in vaccines. This modification is known as a synthetic base exchange. A natural RNA nucleotide is replaced by a modified nucleotide. More specifically, the main component of the base will be replaced, the nucleoside.

The base exchange of uracil with one of these bases, such as m5C, N6-methyladenosine (m6A), Ψ, 5-methyluridine (m5U) and 2-thiouridine (s2U) should reduce the toxic immune response and improve both translation and protein synthesis. In theory, these supposedly nucleoside-modified RNAs should lead to an increased translation by extinguishing protein kinase R activity and reducing PKR-modulated phosphorylation.

The theory and the more or less successful implementation has been proven so far only in mice experiments. However, these studies are not even 10 years old. Andries et al. propose the following In-Vitro studies to justify gene therapy in humans (3):

1. Mikki et al. demonstrated stem cell differentiation in 2015.
2. Wroblewska et al. used artificial gene clusters to kill selected cancer cells in 2015.
3. Korman et al. treated mice with protein B deficiency in 2011
4. Zangi et al. treated mice with myocardial infarction in 2012

5. Mahiny et al. expressed successfully in 2015 zinc finger genome in mice.

And even Andries' experimental study shows the successful nucleoside-modified base exchange with m1 Ψ mRNA just in mice. A single In-Vivo success of a modified gene transfer in mice without long-term studies cannot justify the approval of gene therapy in humans, while completely disregarding the ethical and moral reasons. However, nucleoside modification in humans was only examined in clinical studies until Pfizer introduced nucleoside-modified mRNA with the Covid "vaccines".

Despite, the In-Vivo success of nucleoside-modified mRNA translation in mice, Andries et al. warn that modified mRNA is unsuitable for vaccination, because of the inflammatory immune response it triggers. Precise fine modification of the mRNA would be required in order to make use of such techniques in vaccination.

Furthermore, Andries et al. reported that injections with nucleoside-modified mRNA in humans led already to induced mitochondrial toxicity, liver failure and death during clinical trials. (3). However, this warning was clearly ignored by the Covid vaccine manufacturers like Pfizer.

The artificial base exchange in the Pfizer "vaccine" with modified N1-methylpseudouridine (Y) also harbours another danger. The modified base can enter into a non-specific pairing with any RNA base such as adenosine, guanine, cytosine or uracil, which is not intended in nature, since bases only enter into specific pairings. This can lead to incorrect readings and translation errors with the production of incorrect proteins during protein synthesis. Errors in transcription and translation again lead to alarm cascades, which trigger cancer development, as previously reported with Willaume et al.(5,6,7).

Method

Structural Analyses of the Pfizer "vaccine"

The published WHO paper of Pfizer Vaccines was analyzed for a more detailed examination of the mRNA "vaccine" (8,9). The WHO paper lists and specifies the structure in the Pfizer vaccine and is, therefore, suitable for the structure analyses of the mRNA vaccines.

Gene Code Analyses of the Pfizer "Vaccine"

The original mRNA code was published in the WHO paper. The research group from Stanford led by Dae-Eun Jeong have sequenced the Pfizer mRNA code from a Covid "vaccine" using the reverse genetics method and published the results on Github(10,11).

In addition, by replacing the m1 Ψ -modified pseudo base with thymine, Jeong et al. translated the modified mRNA into RNA.

In order to evaluate the Pfizer mRNA code, this study compared only the Pfizer spike protein Open reading Frame (Figure 1) with the spike protein sequence from the SARS CoV-2 Wuhan-Hu1 virus (Genbank Association: MN908947.3).

Since the original genetic code from the WHO paper is modified, the pseudo base Ψ has to be replaced with the base thymine. This translation has been already conducted by Jeong et al. The published paper by Jeong was, therefore, used for the analogy with the SARS CoV-2 spike protein(10).

Results of the Structural Analyses

The WHO paper shows the genetic code of the mRNA spike protein that is to be read on the reading frame, ORF (Open Reading Frame). However, the spike protein code has been continuously altered by the m1 Ψ -pseudouridine base modification. This complete change of the spike protein gene

coding is found in both Moderna and Pfizer, as reported in Jeong et al.(10). Figure 1 shows a screenshot of the Pfizer mRNA gene code. The continuous gene code modification is clearly visible.

Pfizer and Moderna seem to deliberately ignore that continuous nucleotide exchanges of natural nucleotides with artificial nucleotides for all gene segments can lead to fatal consequences in the translation process (5).

```

GA GAA VAAA C  WAG ΨAVΨCΨΨ  CΨGGΨCCCCA  CAGACΨCAGA  GAGA ACCCGC  50
CACC AVGΨΨC  GΨGΨΨCCΨGG  ΨGCΨGCΨGCC  ΨCΨGGΨGΨCC  AGCCAGΨGΨG  100
ΨGAACΨGAC  CACCAGAACA  CAGCΨGCCΨC  CAGCCΨACAC  CAACAGCΨΨΨ  150
ACCAGAGGCG  ΨGΨACΨACCC  CGACAAGGΨG  ΨΨCAGAVCCA  GCGΨGCΨGCA  200
CΨCΨACCCAG  GACCΨGΨΨCC  ΨGCCΨΨΨCΨΨ  CAGCAACGΨG  ACCΨGGΨΨCC  250
ACGCCAVCCA  CGΨGΨCCGGC  ACCAAΨGGCA  CCAAGAGAΨΨ  CGACAACCCC  300
GΨGCΨGCCΨΨ  ΨCAACGACGG  GGΨGΨACΨΨΨ  GCCAGCACCG  AGAAGΨCCAA  350
CAΨCAΨCAGA  GGCΨGGAΨCΨ  ΨCGGCACCAC  ACΨGGACAGC  AAGACCCAGA  400
GCCΨGCΨGAV  CGΨGAACAAC  GCCACCAACG  ΨGGΨCAΨCAA  AGΨGΨGCGAG  450
ΨΨCCAGΨΨCΨ  GCAACGACCC  CΨΨCCΨGGGC  GΨCΨACΨACC  ACAAGAACAA  500
CAAGAGCΨGG  AΨGGAAGCG  AGΨΨCCGGGΨ  GΨACAGCAGC  GCCAACAAΨΨ  550
GCACCΨΨCGA  GΨACGΨGΨCC  CAGCCΨΨΨCC  ΨGAΨGGACCΨ  GGAAGGCAAG  600
CAGGGCAACΨ  ΨCAAGAACCΨ  GCGCGAGΨΨC  GΨGΨΨΨAAGA  ACAΨCGACGG  650
CΨACΨΨCAAG  AΨCΨACAGCA  AGCACACCCC  ΨAΨCAACCΨC  GΨGCGGGAΨC  700
ΨGCCΨCAGGG  CΨΨCΨCΨGCΨ  CΨGGAACCCC  ΨGGΨGGAΨCΨ  GCCCAΨCGGC  750
AΨCAACAΨCA  CCCGGΨΨΨCA  GACACΨGCGΨ  GCCCΨGCACA  GAAGCΨACCΨ  800
GACACCΨGGC  GAΨAGCAGCA  GCGGAΨGGAC  AGCΨGGΨGCC  GCCGCΨΨACΨ  850
AΨΨGGGGCΨA  CCΨGCAGCCΨ  AGAACΨΨCC  ΨGCΨGAAGΨA  CAACGAGAAC  900

```

Fig. 1 Screenshot of Pfizer mRNA code(8)

According to Morais et al., base modifications with pseudouridine play a major role in Alzheimer dementia, and the development of cancers. The Pfizer "vaccine" not only modified natural bases with pseudouridine, but these pseudo bases were methylated additionally at the base position 1 to ensure stronger base pairing with the modified pseudo-base(12).

- The following structures are requirements for complete protein synthesis of mRNA codes;
- 5-Cap area, exonuclease protection
- 5-UTR non-coding region, start codon
- ORF, Open Reading Frame, open reading frame with actual spike protein code
- 3-UTR non-coding region, stop codon
- Poly A tail

Figure 2 shows how Pfizer has altered the usual mRNA structure by placing two poly-A tails instead of one(13).

Fig.2 Pfizer mRNA structure from Jeeva(13)

Figure 3 lists the elements from the Pfizer "vaccine" structure, which differs from the mRNA structural requirements. Firstly, the initiating 5-UTR start codon binds a Kozak sequence to an alpha globulin gene sequence. Secondly, as already mentioned, the natural base uracil has been replaced by an artificially methylated pseudo-uridine called 1-methyl-3'-pseudouridylyl(8). Thirdly, the 5-cap region was also modified by adding methylations at the first and second bases (m7GpppNmpN, m7GpppNmpNm)(13).

Element	Description	Position
cap	A modified 5'-cap1 structure (m ⁷ G ^m m ³ -5'-ppp-5'-Am)	1-2
5'-UTR	5'-untranslated region derived from human alpha-globin RNA with an optimized Kozak sequence	3-54
sig	S glycoprotein signal peptide (extended leader sequence), which guides translocation of the nascent polypeptide chain into the endoplasmic reticulum.	55-102
S protein_mut	Codon-optimized sequence encoding full-length SARS-CoV-2 spike (S) glycoprotein containing mutations K986P and V987P to ensure the S glycoprotein remains in an antigenically optimal pre-fusion conformation; stop codons: 3874-3879 (underlined)	103-3879
3'-UTR	The 3' untranslated region comprises two sequence elements derived from the amino-terminal enhancer of split (AES) mRNA and the mitochondrial encoded 12S ribosomal RNA to confer RNA stability and high total protein expression.	3880-4174
poly(A)	A 110-nucleotide poly(A)-tail consisting of a stretch of 30 adenosine residues, followed by a 10-nucleotide linker sequence and another 70 adenosine residues.	4175-4284

Fig.3 from the WHO paper(8)

The Kozak sequence is a specific sequence that supports difficult readable gene sequences with the initiation of the translation process. To date, the following established sequence GCCGCCA/GCCAUGG has been used in Eukaryotes.

However, Pfizer and Moderna use a different modified Kozak sequence, namely GCCACCAUG instead of the usual GCCACCAUGGCG, as reported in Xia et al. Thus, the modified Kozak sequence in Pfizer does not follow the principles of Kozak optimization, since a Kozak sequence would likely change the spike protein structure.

According to Xia, the Kozak sequence in the Pfizer vaccine is not a true Kozak sequence. In addition, errors and incompetence are evident in the development of these novel mRNAs. As Xia has already pointed out, wrong codons have been used in the "vaccines" as optimized codons for example in the Moderna "vaccine"(5).

The 5-UTR binding at the alpha globulin does not only stabilize the mRNA, but also lead to faster and secure recognition of the mRNA code by ribosome subunits. Even the stop codon was a botched job. As reported by Xia, disadvantaged combinations of bases were used for the stop codon. The stop codons in human chromosomes have a UAA or at least UGA sequence, while Pfizer uses a UGAU base sequence, which is new territory(5).

However, the Pfizer mRNA sequence shows another striking modification. Two targeted point mutations in the spike protein, change the amino acids lysine and valine to proline at positions 986 and 987 (12). Noticeable is, that the engineering of the spike protein from different recombinant gene fragments was just possible by targeted point mutations. Thus the targeted point mutations in the Pfizer "vaccine" intend to change the spike protein(14).

Supposedly, the point mutations in the Pfizer spike protein intend to turn the spike protein into an antigene and provoke a stronger immune response(12). This indicates that the spike protein gene from the SARS CoV-2 cannot be both translated and replicated in its original structure in human cells(7).

Also noticeable is the human alpha globulin binding to the 5'UTR element. According to studies, such a binding has mRNA stabilizing effect. Chkheidze et al. reported, however, that alpha

globulin-RNA binding could have an additional function, that has not been investigated in detail, yet. Thus, the alpha globulin could increase the binding affinity of recombinant human-animal mRNA (15).

This fact needs to be taken into account, since the spike protein was engineered from recombinant bat-human gene fragments(16). Again, this constructed gene optimization in the mRNA may oppose further risks that have not been yet investigated.

All of the here analysed modifications, including the human alpha globulin binding to the 5'UTR suppose to intensify the gene translation in the human body(13).

Where the synthetic SARS CoV-2 failed translation and replication process in the human cells, the intention with the "vaccines" is to achieve a "super translation" by means of heavily manipulated mRNA injections, with fatal consequences.

However, the mRNA cannot be injected in human cells without the help of specific structures, since the mRNA single strand alone would be ineffective and unstable. The mRNA can only be injected with coated lipid nanoparticles in nano carriers. Based on Jeeva et al., the Pfizer "vaccine" contains 30 µg base-modified, non-replicating, genes of a stable spike protein including a transmembrane domain, that is packaged in a lipid nanoparticle (13).

The lipid nanoparticles consist of cholesterol, phospholipid, ionized lipids and PEG lipids, as presented in Figure 4 (4).

Fig. 4 Lipidnano particle from Elie Dolgin (4)

PEG or polyethene glycol are hydrophilic polymers or also called "softeners" that are used during industrial production in chemistry, cosmetics or the pharmaceutical industry. High allergic response and anaphylactic shock to PEG lipids have been already reported for Pfizer, Moderna and AstraZeneca "vaccines".

Various studies from countries like Sweden, Germany, Great Britain, Spain, and the Netherlands have reported cases with increased allergic reactions to Covid "vaccines".

Allergic reactions on vaccines are proposed by the Swedish study from Nielsson at 1.31 million per vaccinated, which is with 4.7 per million vaccinated significantly higher for the Covid "vaccines by the factor 4 (17).

One reason for the rising allergic reactions on covid "vaccines" is the high concentration of PEG lipids in Pfizer and Moderna. Both Covid "vaccines contain PEG-2000, i.e. 2000 g/mol. According to the Spanish study by Cabanillas, PEG concentrations of <400 g/mol are less toxic, while concentrations of < 3350 g/mol are toxic.

Allergic testing with the skin prick test prior to vaccination might detect and prevent an allergic reaction on PEG (18).

Given the danger that repeated covid injections in a short amount of time lead to the cumulation of PEG concentration, while at the same time allergic testing has been not issued even in the presence of an allergic history of individuals, the covid vaccine manufacturers act grossly negligent. The risk of PEG cumulation is not issued in the vaccine information leaflet.

Interestingly, older studies from the '70s, 80's and 90's have already reported that PEG triggers a non-IgE-related immune response, in the context that IgM and IgG antibodies to PEG were even found in healthy individuals(19). One has to question, whether to the covid vaccine manufacturers make use of PEG lipids not for mRNA stabilization, but intended provocation of an immune reaction, even if at the expense of an allergic reaction.

Noticeable is also that the vaccine manufacturers use different dosages for the same vaccine. Morais reports about different mRNA dosages in the Moderna vaccines. Apparently, the increased dosage of 100 µg was more effective at the cost of increased side effects, while Moderna dosages between 25 and 50 µg were less effective. Therefore, the CureVac mRNA "vaccine" that failed with an effectiveness of 44%, was not approved with a dosage of 12 µg. According to studies, the lower effectiveness is related to a lower translation success(12).

At this point, additional Covid vaccine ingredients are disclosed, which are neither indicated in the package leaflet nor the Pfizer WHO paper. Other Covid "vaccine" components are so-called anorganic or organic nano-objects, which in theory act as immune adjuvants and intend to increase the immune response. Such anorganic nanomaterials are still in clinical trials and are actually not approved.

The addition of adjuvants in vaccines comes from the cancer therapy. Vaccine antigens with adjuvants are delivered in nano carrier, which causes an accumulation of the cells by binding to dendritic cells. The Binding of antigene with adjuvants should supposedly prolong the immune response.

In theory, the genetic code should be stabilized by the addition of anorganic nano materials. And the immune response to the antigene should be both increased and prolonged by avoiding repeated vaccinations. And in addition, the approach should allow an expansion of the disease spectrum to cancer and HIV. The anorganic vaccine adjuvants serve as gene carriers and immune boosters, at the same time.

Li reported that anorganic adjuvants should theoretically reduce the vaccination frequency, but since there are currently no efficient adjuvants, repeated vaccinations have to be carried out for the time being. Thus, future nanoadjuvants in preventive or therapeutic vaccines should enable rational manipulation of the immune system(20).

Moreover, Li recommends the use of anorganic adjuvants for the entire population, including neonates, the elderly, and the immune-suppressed blindly and without issuing warnings. The biased and heroic portrayal of novel gene carriers leaves no room for a critical evaluation of possible side effects. Acute or chronic toxicity of such use are mentioned and dismissed in one breath(20).

The most commonly anorganic vaccine adjuvants are the Mesoporus particles (Figure 5,6). A Mesoporous particle is a metallic, pore containing nanocarrier, which can consist of the following metals/semi-metals: silica, aluminium, iron, copper, cobalt, zinc gold, titanium (20). The main common used, nanoadjuvants are synthetic nanofibers made of silica (Figure 6,11).

The Mesoporous particle serves as a delivery carrier for genetic material or biomolecules and acts at the same time as an immune booster (20,21).

Fig 5. Dendritic Mesoporus(28)

Fig 6. Mesoporus Silica(29)

Fig7. Mesoporus Silica (30)

The unknown nano objects, that were found in Covid “vaccines” by Burkhardt et al., show patterns of metallic crystals (Figure 9) consistent with the Mesoporus zeolites (Figure 8)(22,23). Burkhardt et al. found under the electron microscope, nano-objects from post-mortem covid vaccinated (Figure 10), which correspond with synthetically produced silicon fibers (Figure 11) (23,24,25).

Fig.8 Mesoporus zeolites (22)

Fig.9 Nanoparticles in Covid Vaccine(23)

In Addition, the spectrometry study of the Covid “vaccines” also showed occurrences of iron and chromium (Figure 12).

Fig. 12 Spectrometry of Pfizer vaccine(25)

The findings confirm how manufacturers inconsistently and unsystematically make use of various metallic immune adjuvants in the "vaccines". This study disclosed the unknown foreign nano object findings in vaccines by Burkhardt et al. as metallic immune adjuvants, which were not indicated in the patient information nor in the Pfizer information leaflet(23,26).

Thus, the metallic nano-objects were not contaminations, as initially assumed, but functional usage of metal as immune adjuvants to enhance the immune response.

At this point, it can only be assumed that the findings of stainless steel in the Moderna vaccines by the Japanese research group is also not a matter of contaminations, but of human trial experiments with different immune adjuvants. The fact that the Japanese study, who published traces of stainless steel in the Moderna "vaccine", was deleted from the Internet and PubMed should raise attention to the cover up of injecting toxic metals as part of human experiments(27).

The US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) is well aware of metallic immune adjuvants in vaccines since the FDA had already approved the Mesoporous Silica adjuvant in 2010, but only for human clinical trials(20).

However, if the FDA has approved the Covid vaccines with silica adjuvants, although the adjuvants were only approved for clinical trials, legal consequences would must be considered. And according to the updated studies published on the CDC website, metallic and semi-metallic adjuvants for vaccines, with the exception of aluminium, are not yet approved(20,31).

Just as reverse genetics was used to engineer gene fragments into SARS CoV-2 RNA(14), the reverse vaccinology method was developed to inject mRNA codes selected by computer simulation for delivery into metallic particles coated with lipid nanoparticles(2).

While live or dead antigens of the pathogen are selected and injected as conventional vaccines, in reverse vaccinology the genome of the pathogen is screened by a computer program until suitable gene fragments are found based on two criteria. The gene fragments are ideal for delivery in nanocarriers and have the highest translation success. Figure 13 shows a graphic with the present nanocarriers for Covid "vaccines".

Fig.13 Covid nanocarrier from Chauhan(21)

As reported by Seib et al., the method of computer-assisted Reverse Vaccinology is used to search the entire gene bank for potential code candidates. Seib et al speak of 600 potentially available vaccination codes(2).

Thus, the Reverse Vaccinology approach is not about vaccination or immunization, as the name wrongfully suggests, but about the injection of an optimal genetic code into the human body. Neither therapy nor preventive measures are intended. This is not only computer-aided gene optimization, but mass vaccine production at the expense of human genome experiments.

Results of the Genetic code Analyses

Since the Covid "vaccines are based on computer-assisted gene sequences, the Pfizer mRNA code was examined more closely. Based on the WHO paper, the bases from 103 to 3879 represent the complete gene code for the spike protein. This selected gene sequence was compared base by base, with the spike protein sequence from SARS CoV-2 Wuhan Hu1.

Figure 14 highlighted in colour, the base sequences that match the SARS CoV-2 spike protein. As Figure 14 shows, only small gene fragments from the SARS CoV-2 spike protein have been taken for the Pfizer mRNA. There is only a 24% match between the Pfizer spike protein and the SARS CoV-2 spike protein. Almost **80%** of the genetic code, that has been displayed by Pfizer as the spike protein, consists actually of an **unknown genetic code**. Thus, Pfizer falsely distributes an unknown gene sequence as faked spike protein vaccines.

Fig. 14 Pfizer Gene Code Analyses

Conclusion

The Covid vaccines are not about vaccinations, but about delivering an unknown artificial gene sequence as metallic gene carriers into the human body, as with the Trojan horse. The intended goal is to bypass the human immune system, while it's on the edge of break down, to deliver the foreign gene that manipulates the human genome. Nine techniques were required to completely crash down

the human immune system, while the carrier can pass the human gene expressing alert system.

1. A mRNA was injected with artificially replaced bases
2. The artificial bases were additionally modified to enhance interaction between artificial mRNA and natural human tRNA.
3. The optimizing translation aide (Kosak sequence) was changed
4. The cap region was changed by methylation.
5. The modified stop codons were modified into disadvantaged codons.
6. The actual antigen of the pathogen was changed by two point mutations
7. The binding of alpha globulin enhances the affinity of recombinant animal-human gene combinations, that might have been rejected otherwise.
8. PEG lipids were misused for allergic immune provocation.
9. Metallic immune adjuvants trigger a toxic immune reaction

A total of nine techniques are required for a single injection to completely shut down the human immune system. The metallic adjuvants produce well-known symptoms of poisoning such as silicosis with silica, iron poisoning or chrome poisoning.

This study highly recommends the implementation of toxicology screenings of adjuvants on covid vaccinated, which have been listed by Li(19). Furthermore, to complete the clinical picture of Covid and Covid vaccine side effects, a retrospective toxicological screening of Covid deceased is also strongly recommended.

If the Pfizer “vaccine” were really a new type of vaccine, why have all the established gene expressing processes have been changed that could support the translation success, such as optimized start/stop codons,? Why was an incorrect Kosak sequence used?

And if the mRNA “vaccines” supposedly contain the spike protein of the pathogen, why were only 24% of the pathogen's antigene sequence included?

Why are mRNA products distributed as vaccines, who host 80% of an unknown genome?

And how can such a highly fragmented RNA of a pathogen be translated at all into a functional protein?

And why were metallic and semi-metallic non-approved adjuvants used and not even listed in the package insert or in the WHO Pfizer paper, as per GMP requested (Good Medical Practice)?

Humans are seen here as part of a production chain to satisfy the greed for profit of an entire technology and pharmaceutical industry. The pathogen for the Pfizer mRNA has yet to be developed so that we can even speak of a vaccine. The only effectivity that can be proven with these gene-modified drug products is the effective immune breakdown. And it becomes clear that the complete collapse of the immune system was intended with the combination of high dosage together with the right choice of toxic adjuvants.

If these genome experiments are not stopped with immediate effect, not only could any kind of future artificial gene sequence be delivered into human cells, but possibly all of our DNA bases could be replaced by artificially generated bases. To be very clear. The complete artificial alteration of our genome would lead to an alienation of our kind.

References

1. Joanne M. Willey, Linda M. Sherwood, Christopher J. Woolverton, Prescott, Harley, and Klein's Microbiology. McGraw-Hill, 7th Edition.
2. K. L. Seib, X. Zhao and R. Rappuoli, Developing vaccines in the era of genomics: a decade of reverse vaccinology. *CMI REVIEW*. 2012; 18(5):109-116.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-0691.2012.03939.x>
3. Oliwia Andries, Séan Mc Cafferty, Stefaan C De Smedt, Ron Weiss, Niek N Sanders, Tasuku Kitada, N(1)-methylpseudouridine-incorporated mRNA outperforms pseudouridine incorporated mRNA by providing enhanced protein expression and reduced immunogenicity in mammalian cell lines a..., *Journal of Controlled Release*. 2015, 10:217:337-44.
4. Elie Dolgin, The tangled history of mRNA vaccines. *Nature*. 2021; 9. <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-021-02483-w>
5. Xuhua Xia, Detailed Dissection and Critical Evaluation of the Pfizer/BioNTech and Moderna mRNA Vaccines. *Vaccines*. 2021; 9: 734.
6. Simon Willaume, Emilie Rass, Paula Fontanilla-Ramirez, Angela Moussa, Paul Wanschoor and Pascale Bertrand, A Link between Replicative Stress, Lamin Proteins, and Inflammation. *Genes* 2021; 12: 552.
7. M.A. (2021). Can the SARS CoV-2 be transmitted between humans?
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5762107>
8. WHO International Nonproprietary Names Programme. Berthub.EU.
<https://berthub.eu/articles/11889.doc> [accessed 30/12/2021].
9. Berthub, Reverse Engineering the Source code of the BionTech/Pfizer SARS CoV-2 Vaccine. 2020. <https://berthub.eu/articles/posts/reverse-engineering-source-code-of-the-biontech-pfizer-vaccine/> [Accessed 30/12/2022].
10. Dae-Eun Jeong, Matthew McCoy, Karen Artilles, Orkan Ilbay, Andrew Fire, Kari Nadeau, Helen Park, Brooke Betts, Scott Boyd, Ramona Hoh, and Massa Shoura. Assemblies of putative SARS-CoV2-spike-encoding mRNA sequences for vaccines BNT-162b2 and mRNA-1273. *Virological.org*. 2021. <https://virological.org/t/assemblies-of-putative-sars-cov2-spike-encoding-mrna-sequences-for-vaccines-bnt-162b2-and-mrna-1273/663> [Accessed 6.1.2022].
11. Github, NAnalytics, Assemblies of putative SARS CoV-2 spike encoding mRNA Sequence for vaccines BNT 162b2 and mRNA 1273. 2021. <https://github.com/NAalytics/Assemblies-of-putative-SARS-CoV2-spike-encoding-mrna-sequences-for-vaccines-BNT-162b2-and-mRNA-1273/blob/main/Assemblies%20of%20putative%20SARS-CoV2-spike-encoding%20mRNA%20sequences%20for%20vaccines%20BNT-162b2%20and%20mRNA-1273.docx.pdf> [Accessed 30/12/2022].
12. Pedro Morais, Hironori Adachi and Yi-Tao Yu, The Critical Contribution of Pseudouridine to mRNA COVID-19 Vaccines. *Frontiers in Cell and Developmental Biology*. 2021; 9
13. Subbiah Jeeva, Ki-Hye Kim, Chong Hyun Shin, Bao-Zhong Wang and Sang-Moo Kang, An Update on mRNA-Based Viral Vaccines. *Vaccines* 2021, 9, 965.
14. M.A. (2021). The Story about the constructed SARS COV-2 Virus - A Review of three Research Groups. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4570941>
15. Alexander N. Chkheidze, Dmitry L. Lyakhov, Alexander V. Makeyev, Julia Morales, Jian Kong, and Stephen A. Liebhaber, Assembly of the α -Globin mRNA Stability Complex Reflects Binary Interaction between the Pyrimidine-Rich 3' Untranslated Region Determinant and Poly(C) Binding Protein aCP. *Molecular And Cellular Biology*. 1999; 19(7): p. 4572-458.
16. M.A. (2021). Emergence of synthetic recombinant bat-human spike protein in the Wuhan SARS CoV-2. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4532195> .
17. Lennart Nilsson, Agnes Csuth, Jann Storsaeter, Lene H. Garvey, and Maria C.

- Jenmalm, Vaccine allergy: evidence to consider for COVID-19 vaccines. *Curr Opin Allergy Clin Immunol*. 2021; 21(4): 401–409.
18. Beatriz Cabanillas, Natalija Novak, Allergy to COVID-19 vaccines: A current update. *Allergology International*. 2021; 70: 313-318.
 19. Jörg Kleine-Tebbe, Ludger Klimek, Eckard Hamelmann, Oliver Pfaar, Christian Taube, Martin Wagenmann, Thomas Werfel, and Margitta Worm, Severe allergic reactions to the COVID-19 vaccine – statement and practical consequences. *Allergologie select*. 2021; 5: 6-28.
 20. Xia Li, Xiupeng Wang and Atsuo Ito, Tailoring inorganic nanoadjuvants towards next-generation vaccines. *The Royal Society of Chemistry*. 2018. DOI: 10.1039/c8cs00028j.
 21. Gaurav Chauhan, Marc J. Madou, Sourav Kalra, Gianni Chopra, Deepa Ghosh, and Sergio O. Martinez-Chapa, Nanotechnology for COVID-19: Therapeutics and Vaccine Research. *ACS Nano*. 2020; 14(7): 7760–7782.
 22. Molecular Nanotechnology Lab. Mesoporous zeolites for refining applications. <https://nanomol.es/mesoporous-zeolites-refining-applications/> [Accessed 5.1.2022].
 23. Pathologie-Konferenz, Tod nach Covid Impfung. 2021. https://www.pathologie-konferenz.de/Tod_nach_COVID-19-Impfung_www_pathologie-konferenz_de.pdf. [accessed 5.1.2022].
 24. Chuanubin Mao, Fuke Wang, Binrui Cao, Controlling Nanostructures of Mesoporous Silica Fibers by Supramolecular Assembly of Genetically Modifiable Bacteriophages. *20. Angewandte Chemie International Edition*. 2012; 51(26): 6411-5.
 25. Arne Burkhardt, Walter Lang, Werner Bergholz, Pathologie-Konferenz.de-Todesursache nach Covid-19 Impfung. 2021. <https://www.pathologie-konferenz.de> . 2021 [accessed 29.11.2021].
 26. Pfizer, Package Leaflet: Information for the user. October 2021. <http://labeling.pfizer.com/ShowLabeling.aspx?id=15502> [Accessed 9.1.2022].
 27. Rocky Swift and Carl O'donnell, Reuters: Moderna to recall COVID-19 doses in Japan after stainless steel contaminants found. September 2021. <https://www.reuters.com/business/healthcare-pharmaceuticals/japan-finds-stainless-steel-particles-suspended-doses-moderna-vaccine-2021-09-01/> [Accessed 10.1.2022].
 28. Jing Hu, Peiting Du, Ruoyi Xu, and Weijun Deng, Supersmall Dendritic Mesoporous Silica Nanospheres as Antioxidant Nanocarriers for Pickering Emulsifiers. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*. 2021; 69(49), 14893-14905.
 29. Wikipedia Commons. File, Radial mesoporous silica. https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Radial_mesoporous_silica.jpg [Accessed 5.1.2022].
 30. Miguel Manzano, María Vallet-Regí, Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles for Drug Delivery. *Adv. Funct. Mater* 2020; 30(2).
 31. CDC.gov. Adjuvants and Vaccines. <https://www.cdc.gov/vaccinesafety/concerns/adjuvants.html> [Accessed 11.1.2022].